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науково-практична конференція
студентів та молодих
вчених із міжнародною участю

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**ІННОВАЦІЇ в
МЕДИЦИНІ та ФАРМАЦІЇ**
**INNOVATIONS in
MEDICINE and PHARMACY**

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ABSTRACT BOOK | ТЕЗИ ДОПОВІДЕЙ

МІНІСТЕРСТВО ОХОРОНИ ЗДОРОВ'Я УКРАЇНИ
ІВАНО-ФРАНКІВСЬКИЙ НАЦІОНАЛЬНИЙ МЕДИЧНИЙ УНІВЕРСИТЕТ
ТОВАРИСТВО МОЛОДИХ ВЧЕНИХ
СТУДЕНТСЬКЕ НАУКОВЕ ТОВАРИСТВО

ТЕЗИ ДОПОВІДЕЙ

92-ї науково-практичної конференції студентів та
молодих вчених із міжнародною участю
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ABSTRACTS

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Nigeria, 32.4% from Poland, and 40.5% from Ukraine. The survey was anonymous and carried out using a 20-question questionnaire.

Results. It was established that a significant number of those examined during the specified period after suffering from COVID-19 had the following symptoms: chest discomfort (50%, 41.2%, and 53%), cough (60%, 50%, and 60%), shortness of breath (30%, 33.3%, and 40%), increased blood glucose levels (0, 25% and 26.7%) in Nigerians, Poles, and Ukrainians, respectively. Respondents also indicated other symptoms: headache, dizziness, general weakness, skin changes, and manifestations from the digestive tract.

Conclusions.

1. Post-covid syndrome is a multidisciplinary problem that requires the attention of specialists from different countries of the world.
2. In order to improve the quality of life, it is necessary to personalize recommendations for rehabilitation and treatment of complications for each patient.

THE ASSOCIATION BETWEEN NONALCOHOLIC FATTY LIVER DISEASE AND ATRIAL FIBRILLATION: KEY INDICATORS OF THEIR CO-EXISTENCE

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Introduction. The prevalence of Nonalcoholic fatty liver disease (NAFLD) and atrial fibrillation (AF) has increased globally in recent years. According to recent studies, NAFLD and AF affect approximately 32% and 0.51% of the general population respectively.

Aim. To investigate the association between NAFLD and AF by utilizing the FibroTest-4 (FIB-4) and Nonalcoholic Fatty Liver Score (NFS) indices and measuring periostin levels.

Materials and methods. In this study, we enrolled 96 patients diagnosed with NAFLD that attended State Institution «Territorial medical association of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of Ukraine in Ivano-Frankivsk region» to investigate the association between NAFLD and AF. The study population was divided into two groups: main group - 35 patients with both NAFLD and AF, and control group - 61 patients with NAFLD only. Full blood count was performed on HTI MICROCC-20PLUS. Biochemical tests were performed on HTI BioChem SA Semi-Auto Chemistry Analyzer BC-3002-C-UA. All patients had their abdominal ultrasound investigation to confirm NAFLD using the SonoScape S20. To assess liver fibrosis the following non-invasive indices were used: The FibroTest-4 (FIB-4) index and the Nonalcoholic Fatty Liver Score (NFS). Periostin was measured by ELISA method using the HTI ImmunoChem-2100, and Human Periostin/OSF2 ELISA Kit PicoKine®. The statistical analysis for this study was conducted using IBM SPSS Statistics version 26.0.

Results. The NAFLD + AF group also had higher levels of periostin (10.8 ± 1.6 ng/ml vs. 9.8 ± 1.75 ng/ml, $p < 0.001$) and higher NFS (-1.05 ± 1.46 vs. -2.65 ± 1.63 , $p < 0.001$) and FIB-4 score (1.34 ± 0.86 vs. 1.07 ± 0.6 , $p = 0.048$). Periostin was found to associate with the risk of NAFLD + AF with an OR of 2.079 (95% CI: 1.418 – 3.048, $p < 0.001$). Similar results were with NFS (OR=3.233, 95% CI: 1.970 - 5.303, $p < 0.001$) and FIB-4 (OR=2.498, 95% CI: 1.109 – 5.627, $p = 0.027$). The receiver operating characteristic (ROC) analysis was performed on three variables, NFS, FIB-4 and periostin, to determine their ability to distinguish between patients with NAFLD + AF and NAFLD only. The results showed that NFS had the highest area under the curve (AUC) with a value of 0.868 (95% CI: 0.792-0.943, $p < 0.001$), indicating excellent discriminatory ability. FIB-4 had an AUC of 0.651 (95% CI: 0.537-0.765, $p = 0.014$), while periostin had an AUC of 0.759 (95% CI: 0.660-0.858, $p < 0.001$).

Conclusions. These findings suggest a strong association between NAFLD and AF, and highlights the importance of considering AF as a potential complication in patients with NAFLD. The use of the FIB-4 and NFS indices and measurement of periostin levels proved to be effective in detecting this association.